

An implementation of the Li&Stephens HMM for read data

Stephan Scholz*, Alexander Dilthey
Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf

June 22, 2025

1 Problem description

We want to infer genomic sequence of an individual, conditional on observed reads and a reference panel (genome inference). The genomic sequence of interest could be a chromosome or a genetic region, in any case it is much longer than reads produced by current sequencing technologies. We also have assembled sequences for R haplotypes randomly chosen from the population the individual of interest originates from. In the process of sequence assembly, it is often useful to start with an approximation of the wanted sequence, e.g. for scaffolding or in the case of reference guided assembly. Our goal is to infer such an approximation based on our knowledge of population haplotypes and read data for the individual. We employ the model presented here in the assembly of the Human Leukocyte Antigen (HLA or MHC) locus, a highly diverse ≈ 5 Mb long region on chromosome 6, but the method is not specific to this region.

2 Approach

Li and Stephens worked on a similar problem [2]. For sequence imputation, they devised a hidden markov model (HMM) that approximates the new haplotype by joining segments of the population haplotypes. Their model assumes the new haplotype can be created via homologous recombination from the population haplotypes. Duplications, inversions and translocations that are not present in the population sample will not be incorporated into the approximated haplotype and have to be handled by subsequent steps if desired. This is often an acceptable limitation, as in sexually reproducing organisms, homologous recombination occurs frequently during meiosis and the other variations mentioned are rare germline mutations.

We use this setup, adapted for read data.

*to whom correspondence should be addressed, Stephan.Scholz@med.uni-duesseldorf.de

Figure 1: Conceptual setup. Top shows the MSA of known reference haplotypes. Gaps mark structural variants where the haplotypes do not align. Vertical dashed lines mark SNP positions. The new haplotype is a mosaic of segments of the reference haplotypes. It can be represented as path in the MSA (black line).

3 Model description

We start with the MHC sequences of R reference haplotypes. Out of segments of these, we want to create one or two sequences (for homozygous or heterozygous samples) that agree best with our read data and prior information about correlation between close variants (linkage disequilibrium / LD) as observed in our reference set. Let us first consider the case of a sample that is homozygous over the sequence, the reads of which are equivalent to that of an haploid sample. We will generalize to the heterozygous case more common in diploid organisms later. Imagine a horizontal multiple sequence alignment (MSA) of our reference sequences. The new sequence we want to generate is now a path in the grid of references (figure 1). At fixed positions the path can jump from the reference it copied in to another reference. Locally, a jump is only possible within haplotypes that align to each other. Otherwise we would truncate an indel at a position not yet observed in nature, which we forbid. The easiest case is to only allow jumps at positions where all references align to each other. As proposed by Li&Stephens, we will use SNP alleles to determine which haplotype the sample is locally most similar to. Therefore, to divide the reference sequences into segments, we use SNPs present in all haplotypes. Each segment (other than the first and last) starts and ends with a SNP.

After multiple sequence alignment of the R reference sequences (with e.g. mafft [1]), we find all SNP positions by

1. remembering all base positions in the MSA where not all sequences are the same and none of the reference sequences has a gap and
2. only keep differences flanked on both sides by some minimal length (here 5bp) where all sequences are the same.

For a precise probabilistic treatment, Li&Stephens framed the problem as a

hidden markov model (HMM). HMMs are a well studied statistical tool and efficient methods to solve them are available¹. An HMM consists of three parts: start probabilities π to begin in one of the hidden states, transition probabilities a between the hidden states, emission probabilities b of the observable from a hidden state.

Let $t \in [0, T - 1]$ enumerate the position of the T SNPs and $\lambda = (s, (n, m), a_{ij}, b, \pi)$ be an HMM with $s = \{s_i\}$, $s_i \in [0, S - 1]$ the states, $(m, n)_{t,i}$ the observed bases that agree and disagree with base of s_i at t . $\vec{X} \in S^T$ is a path through our MSA, that describes from which haplotype $X_t = s_i$ we are copying from at SNP t (we use the vector arrow to emphasize the distinction of scalars from multidimensional values, but will not use any vector properties). In accordance with Li&Stephens we set

1. initial probabilities: $\pi_i = P(X_0 = s_i) = \frac{1}{S}$
2. transition probabilities: $a_{ij} = P(X_t = s_j | X_{t-1} = s_i) = \begin{cases} e + (1 - e)/S & i = j \\ (1 - e)/S & \text{else} \end{cases}$
with
 $e = \exp(-4Nc\Delta_{t,t-1}/S)$
 $N \dots$ effective population size
 $c \dots$ average recombination rate
 $\Delta_{t,t-1} \dots$ average base pair difference between SNP at $t - 1$ and t
3. emission probabilities: $b = P(Y_t = (m, n) | X_t = s_i) = (1 - \epsilon)^m \cdot \epsilon^n$
with $\epsilon \dots$ read error rate

From these probabilities we can calculate the probability of any path \vec{X} given the SNP alleles \vec{Y} from our reads and our HMM as

$$\begin{aligned}
P(\vec{X} | \vec{Y}, \lambda) &= P(X_0 = s_i) \\
&\quad \cdot P(X_1 = s_j | X_0 = s_i) \cdot P(Y_1 = (m, n)_1 | X_1 = s_j) \\
&\quad \cdot P(X_2 = s_k | X_1 = s_j) \cdot P(Y_2 = (m, n)_2 | X_2 = s_k) \\
&\quad \dots \\
&= \pi_i \cdot a_{ij} \cdot b_1 \cdot a_{jk} \cdot b_2 \cdot \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

A few remarks:

- The probabilities to begin in a particular state are uniform, because we have not made use of any SNP data.
- The transition probabilities are normalized: $\sum_{j=1}^S a_{ij} = 1$. The probability to transition to another state is low for short SNP distances, and increases with distance. The probability to stay on the haplotype is always higher than to jump, but approaches the probability to jump asymptotically. In principle $\Delta_{t,t-1}$ is dependent on the haplotype, as some haplotypes may have deletions between $t - 1$ and t . This would destroy the

¹See Rabiner's tutorial on HHMs (<https://www.cs.ubc.ca/~murphyk/Bayes/rabiner.pdf>)

Figure 2: Principle of mutation substates. For three SNPs, the mutation substates are shown. Without substates and with many reads, the path would follow the dashed arrow. With substates, the path stays in the first haplotype.

normalization and bias the model to create longer haplotypes. For this reason $\Delta_{t,t-1}$ is averaged over the reference haplotypes.

- To obtain the variables n and m for each state at position t , we map the reads against the human reference genome with any of its MHC sequences removed and all of our reference MHC sequences added. Since we know the SNP positions for each reference from the MSA, we can check for each read aligned to any of the MHC sequences if it overlaps an SNP and if, which allele it carries.
- We further introduce mutation substates (see next subsection).

The last two points are our extensions in this model.

3.1 Mutation substates

In cases where the SNP of the sample mutated relative to an otherwise similar reference sequence and with high read depth, the emission probability may become low, thereby forcing a transition to another haplotype. Instead of switching states back and forth, the HMM may take a mutation penalty and stay in a mutation substate of the current state (figure 2). Mathematically, this is modeled as multiplication with the substate transition probability α . Unmutated bases are modeled as substates with a high self-transition probability:

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} 1 - \mu & \text{for the base of the underlying haplotype} \\ \frac{\mu}{3} & \text{for one of the other three bases} \end{cases}$$

with $\mu = 10^{-3} \dots$ mutation rate

Whenever we use the transition probability a_{ij} , it is in fact the transition probability $a_{ij}\alpha$ and every maximization is taken over the four substates.

Figure 3: Calculation of the first three cells in the Viterbi step. Only two values have to be considered to maximize probability $t \rightarrow t + 1$. Orange square: maximum of column. Green lines signify multiplication with a_{ij} . Thick green lines emphasize that a_{ii} is larger than the other.

3.2 Optimized Viterbi solution

Coming up with these probabilities is the main work when describing a problem as a HMM. Our task is to find the path \vec{X} that maximizes $P(\vec{X}|\vec{Y}, \lambda)$. This can be efficiently calculated step wise. For each state, we move forward the path with the maximum probability. Let $v_t(i)$ be the maximum probability over all possible paths that end at SNP t in state i .

$$v_t(i) = \max_{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{t-1}} P(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_t = i | Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_t, \lambda)$$

To calculate these probabilities at the next position, we calculate the probabilities of all possible steps one could take to end up in state j (analogous to equation (1)) and choose the one that maximizes the probability.

$$v_{t+1}(j) = \max_i (v_t(i) a_{ij}) b_j(Y_{t+1})$$

We also have to remember the i 's that maximized the probability in an $S \times (T-1)$ table, to be able to retrace our choice. This is known as the Viterbi algorithm. Since we consider S possible steps for each state, the complexity scales with $S^2 \times (T-1)$. At the last SNP position, one takes the path with the highest probability over all states. From this path, the mosaic sequence is assembled.

Since at each step $t \rightarrow t + 1$ we have only two possible values for the transition probability, namely to stay in the state, $a_{\text{stay}} = a_{ii}$ or perform a jump, $a_{\text{jump}} = a_{ij}, i \neq j$, we can simplify the calculation further. There are only two transitions that compete to maximize the probability: one where the maximum value $v_{t,\text{max}} = \max_i v_t(i)$ of the probabilities is multiplied by the jump probability a_{jump} or $v_t(i) \cdot a_{\text{stay}}$

$$\vec{v}_{t+1} = \max(v_{t,\text{max}} a_{\text{jump}}, \vec{v}_t a_{\text{stay}}), i \neq j$$

Here, the elementwise maximum between a scalar and a vector is taken. (figure 3). In this way, the time complexity becomes linear in the number of states.

3.3 Diploid case

When generalizing to the diploid case, the new states become a pair of the reference haplotypes, $s \rightarrow (s_I, s_{II})$, and we have to adjust the transition and

Figure 4: Diploid state space with example path (left). Equivalent path pair in haploid state space and predicted haplotypes (right).

Figure 5: The four values we have to compare for the next Viterbi step. Increasing saturation of green mark increasing transition probabilities from that cell. Marked in orange and red are column, row and global maxima.

emission probabilities:

1. initial probabilities: $\pi'_i = P(X_0 = s_i) = \frac{1}{S} = \frac{1}{R^2}$
2. transition probability: $a'_{Ri+k, Rj+l} = a_{ij} \cdot a_{kl}$
3. emission probability: $b' = \begin{cases} (1 - \epsilon)^m \cdot \epsilon^n & \text{if SNP is homozygous} \\ 0.5^m \cdot \epsilon^n & \text{if SNP is heterozygous} \end{cases}$

The optimization step is performed analogous to the haploid HMM, but now we have to consider four different values for the maximum value: global, column and row maxima and the previous probability of that element, all multiplied with the appropriate transition probability.

$$v_{ij,t+1} = \max \left(\max_{kl} v_{kl,t} a_{jump}^2, \max_m v_{im,t} a_{stay} a_{jump}, \max_n v_{nj,t} a_{stay} a_{jump}, v_{ij,t} a_{stay}^2 \right)$$

where v_{ij} is taken to be matrix of dimension $R \times R$. See figure 5.

4 Discussion and summary

We adapted the Li&Stephens model for read data. We also introduced mutation substates and performed an optimization that reduces runtime from being quadratic to being linear in the number of reference haplotypes. In this way, we approximate a new haplotype as being a mosaic of reference haplotypes. Inherited from the Li&Stephens approach, we use limited information from the read data. Only SNP alleles are extracted from the reads and structural variants are selected for inclusion solely based on their linkage with surrounding SNPs. The method also relies on the quality of a multiple sequence alignment, which is still challenging to produce for the MHC region.

References

- [1] Kazutaka Katoh, John Rozewicki, and Kazunori D Yamada. Mafft online service: multiple sequence alignment, interactive sequence choice and visualization. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, 20(4):1160–1166, 09 2017.
- [2] Na Li and Matthew Stephens. Modeling linkage disequilibrium and identifying recombination hotspots using single-nucleotide polymorphism data. *Genetics*, 165(4):2213–2233, 12 2003.